

Application of pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) for the determination of some important antibiotics

Bijyendra Kumar Dubey and I. C. Shukla*

Department of Chemistry University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

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A quick and convenient method has been developed for determination of some antibiotic drugs in low concentration. Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the antibiotics are allowed to react with $3 \times 10^{-2} N$ pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) in the presence of $5 N H_2SO_4$ for 5–60 min at RT (25–30°). After the reaction is over, the unconsumed reagent is back determined iodometrically. The value of % error, SD and CV prove the method to be precise and reproducible.

Antibiotics are chemotherapeutic agents needed in low concentration to bring about their action. Because of their antibacterial activity their determination has widely been studied^{1–13}. Most of the above methods involve instrumentation and complicated techniques. In the present paper we describe a simple and convenient method for the determination of some antibiotics with PCC reagent.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration and amount of reagent and sulphuric acid and reaction temperature. Variation in reaction time was found to influence the reaction. In the determination of Ampicillin trihydrate, Amoxycillin trihydrate, Benzathine penicillin G, Cephalexin, Cefadroxil monohydrate and Cefuroxime sodium in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations, constant results were obtained at 10, 5, 10, 15, 45, 60 and 50 min respectively. A much more reaction

time than the prescribed one does not improve the results. The percentage recovery of the sample was fairly low at a lesser reaction time due to incomplete reaction. It was established that the prescribed concentration of the reagent ($3 \times 10^{-2} N$) was suitable for accurate results. Similarly the effect of concentration of PCC and sulphuric acid was studied and it was found that the recommended concentration of both reagents is suitable for the reaction. While studying the effect of temperature, it was observed that the reaction is completed at RT (25–30°). On heating the reaction mixture directly on flame or on water bath, gives inaccurate results. It may be due to decomposition of the reagent. Results given in Table 1 show % error, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV). This indicates that the suggested method is reproducible and precise. It can easily be adopted in a pharmaceutical laboratory. Results for 1 mg sample are given in Table 1. The methods is equally applicable upto 10 mg sample size.

Table 1. Determination of some antibiotics in the pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations with ($3 \times 10^{-2} N$) PCC reagent

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount present* (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molarity	Amount obtained by calculation** (mg)	Error (%)	SD (mg)	CV (%)
1.	Ampicillin trihydrate (pure)	1	0.998	10	2	0.989	-0.95	0.0056	0.5662
	(a) Ampicillin (Cap)	1	0.962	10	2	0.953	-0.98	0.0020	0.2099
	(b) Broadicillin (I)	1	0.969	10	2	0.959	-1.00	0.0015	0.1564
2.	Amoxycillin trihydrate (pure)	1	0.994	5	2	0.985	-0.95	0.0025	0.2538
	(a) Mox (Cap)	1	0.954	5	2	0.944	-1.05	0.0018	0.1907
	(b) Symoxyl (I)	1	0.965	5	2	0.956	-0.91	0.0018	0.1883

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

3.	Benzathine penicillin G (pure)	1	0.980	10	2	0.970	-1.00	0.0028	0.2887
	(a) Penidure (I)	1	0.973	10	2	0.963	-0.98	0.0028	0.2908
	(b) Longacillin (I)	1	0.978	10	2	0.968	-1.02	0.0021	0.2169
4.	Cloxacillin sodium (pure)	1	0.962	15	2	0.953	-0.93	0.0032	0.3358
	(a) Bioclox (I)	1	0.967	15	2	0.958	-0.97	0.0028	0.2923
5.	Cephalexin (pure)	1	0.931	45	2	0.922	-1.00	0.0026	0.2820
	(a) Phexin (Cap)	1	0.926	45	2	0.917	-0.97	0.0029	0.2659
6.	Cefadroxil monohydrate (pure)	1	0.870	60	2	0.861	-1.00	0.0024	0.2787
	(a) Odoxil (T)	1	0.868	60	2	0.860	-0.93	0.0024	0.2791
7.	Cefuroxime sodium (pure)	1	0.989	50	2	0.979	-0.99	0.0022	0.2247
	(a) Supacef (I)	1	0.977	50	2	0.967	-1.01	0.0025	0.2585

Cap = Capsule, I = Injection, T = Tablet

*In each sample nine estimations were done. **Average of nine determinations.

The number of moles of the PCC reagent consumed for the sample depends upon the structure of the antibiotics. On the basis of molecularity and available literature, a possible course of reaction may also be suggested for each compound. All the drugs studied by us belong to penicillin and cephalosporin group, which contain easily oxidisable sulphur atom. On the basis of available literature⁶, it may be proposed that the reagent gives corresponding oxidised products. Depending upon the structure of the compound different oxidised products may be obtained. With the proposed method it was observed that the excipient, if present in the pharmaceutical preparations do not interfere in the determination.

Experimental

PCC solution ($3 \times 10^{-2} N$): The reagent was synthesised in laboratory⁴ and standardised iodometrically. Aqueous solutions of sodium thiosulphate (0.01 N, Merck), Potassium dichromate (0.01 N, Qualigens), Potassium iodide (10% w/v, Baker), starch solution (10% w/v, Merck) were also prepared.

Sample solution: The sample solution (1 mg/ml) of pure antibiotics such as Ampicillin, Amoxycillin, Benzathine penicillin, Cloxacillin sodium, Cephalexin, Cefadroxil monohydrate and Cefuroxime sodium were prepared in distilled water.

Tablet: Twenty tablets were crushed to a fine powder and the powder equivalent to 100 mg of sample was taken in 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in distilled water.

Capsule: Twenty capsules containing a particular antibiotic were taken and the drug present inside the capsule was mixed properly. Amount equivalent to 100 mg of this sample was taken and dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water as usual.

Injection: Amount equivalent to 100 mg of the pure sample was taken and dissolved, in distilled water, as usual, in 100 ml volumetric flask.

Procedure: An aliquot containing 1–5 mg of the sample was taken in 100 ml stoppered conical flask followed by the addition of 5 ml of PCC reagent and 10 ml of 5 N sulphuric acid. The reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to react at RT (25–30°) for prescribed reaction time. After the reaction is over, 5 ml of 10% potassium iodide was added to it and titrated against standardised sodium thiosulphate solution (0.01 N) to starch end point. A blank experiment was also performed under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression.

$$\text{mg of the sample} = \frac{M \times N (B - S)}{n}$$

where, M = mol. wt. of the sample, N = normality of sodium thiosulphate solution, B = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank, S = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample, n = number of moles of PCC consumed per mole of the sample.

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